

RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS OF HUMAN RESOURCES POLICY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

Jumanov Tulkin Sattarovich

Deputy Head of the Department of Spiritual and Educational Work and
Personnel Management of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the
Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8068131>

Abstract: This article gives a systematic overview of the history of the militia system of the Uzbek SSR in relation to human resources policy on the basis of the analysis of sources and research papers related to this topic.

Key words: militia, personnel training, people's commissariat, selection of militia personnel, training mechanisms.

The current human resources policy of internal affairs bodies in our country has a rich history, and its foundation is directly linked to the formation of the Uzbek SSR. It is appropriate to begin the study of this part of history with the processes after the February coup of 1917. After the coup, the Soviet authorities abandoned the militia and gendarmerie, which had previously controlled order and tranquility among the people. The Soviets replaced the militia and gendarmerie with a temporary people's militia. In some places the workers' and peasants' militia of the regions and counties was established [1].

On November 10, 1917 a resolution of the People's Commissariat of Internal Affairs (NKVD) on the "Workers' Militia" was adopted, and the activities of this body came into force. According to this decision, the military and civil authorities were to provide the workers' militia with weapons and appropriate technical forces. The Soviets of Workers' and Soldiers' Deputies approved the staff of the workers' militia. The militia performed its duties on behalf of the Soviets and acted as a state body. Despite this, there were almost no permanent employees in the militia, and mostly hardworking, volunteer enthusiasts were recruited from specialized organizations [2].

At that time, the following requirements were established for a candidate for service in the city militia: "...no younger than 25 years, not below 171 cm in height, pleasant appearance, physically strong, healthy, fluent in speech, having completed military service and being in the army reserve". [3].

In the first years of Soviet power the workers' and peasants' militia did not yet have a personnel apparatus, and the functions of selection, placement and transfer of personnel were carried out at the district (county) level - the district (county) militia and at the regional (province) level - the Soviet regional (province) executive body assigned to the committees. It was at this time that the need for a certain system of personnel accounting arose. And on July 1, 1918, the NKVD created a "personnel accounting table" related to the order of admission, dismissal, transfer and personnel service [3].

The adoption on October 13, 1918 of the joint instruction "On the Establishment of the Soviet Workers' and Peasants' Militia" (NKVD and NKJ) contributed to the strengthening of the organizational structure of the militia, the development of the administrative and legal and organizational basis of personnel-related activities. This instruction strengthened and

further developed the principle of the class approach to the selection and appointment of militia officers. At that time there was a system of personnel records in the district and city militia departments, in which handwritten personnel books were kept and a separate alphabetical card was created for each employee. During recruitment the general and military training of the candidate and the level of political conscience of the candidate were checked by the head of the local militia body, and the decision on the appointment of the officer was made by the head of the local militia body. At that time, not all candidates who participated in the competition met the requirements, but due to the acute shortage of personnel in the militia, almost all candidates were hired [4].

Under this joint instruction, entry into the Soviet militia was free, but the obligation to work for one year after enlistment was established. Soviet militia:

- a) citizens of the Russian Socialist Federal Soviet Republic;
- b) who had reached the age of 21;
- c) fully literate;

g) exercising active and passive suffrage to the Soviets of Deputies in accordance with the Constitution of the USSR;

- e) those who recognized Soviet power could go to work.

The following persons were prohibited from joining the Soviet militia:

- 1) persons accused of a crime, under investigation and trial;
- 2) those restricted or deprived by a court of legal capacity, as well as those engaged in theft, fraud, robbery of entrusted property, forgery, extortion, bribery, usury, and speculation;
- (3) Those who live on non-labor income, that is, those who derive their income from capital or any property;
- 4) all private entrepreneurs and commercial intermediaries;
- (5) Ministers and agents, comrades of former gendarmerie units and former militia units, and members of the former imperial house;
- 6) persons recognized as mentally ill, deaf and dumb [5].

On 29 January 1918 the Council of People's Commissars of Turkestan announced an order № 17 "On the creation of the reserve and reorganization of the militia". On January 30, 1918 the "Department of Militia Inspection of Cities and Volosts of Turkestan Region" was created in order to organize the new militia and manage the training of personnel. In February 1918, militia bodies were established in all counties, cities, and volosts [6].

Also on June 26, 1919, the People's Commissariat of Internal Affairs of the Turkestan ASSR adopted "Regulations on the Soviet Workers and Peasants Militia of the Russian Soviet Federation in the Turkestan ASSR." This Statute also preserved the requirements for joining the Soviet militia.

By the end of 1920 there were 34 city, 26 county, and 92 district militia departments in the Turkestan ASSR. When the Main Department of Militia under the NKVD was established in Turkestan, there were departments of criminal investigation, railway, industrial, water and judicial militia, as well as special volunteer militia units (mainly at the expense of the local population).

In addition to fighting crime, the workers' and peasants' militia played a key role in implementing the decisions, orders, directives and instructions sent by the Center to the NKVD of Turkestan ASSR. At the same time, initially the activities of the workers' and peasants' militia in our territory were accompanied by many conflicting situations. On the one

hand, the existing regime used it as the main link in exercising its power. On the other hand, the main task of the militia, which was to ensure public peace, was unsatisfactorily fulfilled. Due to the low level of knowledge and skills of militia officers, their lack of experience, as well as failure to provide material supplies in a timely manner, corruption, greed, abuse of power, and drunkenness increased in the ranks of the militia. Mainly the ignorance of the language and customs of the local population by the chiefs of militia appointed from the center, and the lack of local personnel weakened the trust of the population in the militia. Similar negative situations were observed in later periods of the Soviet system [7].

A new stage in the development of the Soviet militia began on May 24, 1922, with the adoption of the Regulation on the NKVD of the RSFSR and the abolition of the Regulation "On Workers' and Peasants' Militia". Since this Regulation did not correspond to the situation that arose in the country as a result of political and economic changes. According to the new Provision, the statistical work on accounting and reporting was carried out by the militia department [8].

On November 23, 1922 the Resolution of the Central Executive Committee of the RSFSR "On the revision and retraining of militia officers" and the Order of the Central Executive Committee of the RSFSR "On the training and retraining of militia officers" regulated the work of the militia officers. Also implemented improvements in the quality of personnel and normative-legal documents aimed at recruiting officers to the ranks of the militia [9].

On December 29, 1922 order № 602 of the chief of the republican militia approved the rules of personal account of the militia officers. According to them, personal records were kept by the employees of the Main Administration of the NKVD, the UNKVD Registration and Distribution Department, the Main Administration of the Administrative District, the Regional Executive Committee, the Regional Executive Committee, and the District Department of Militia. The main records consisted of personal sheets and registration cards, as well as a detailed list of employees. They were aimed at collecting the necessary information about the persons considered in them. Thus, beginning in 1922, the primary personnel records were established [10].

In 1924, the NKVD of the RSFSR was created as part of the NKVD of the RSFSR to develop the personnel base of the NKVD, the order and methodology of service records. In accordance with the Statute of October 20, 1924 "On the registration and distribution department of the NKVD and materials on the account of responsible employees", the head of the regional department was in charge of the accounting and distribution work [11].

Already at that time, the issue of improving mechanisms for the selection, placement, and training of Soviet militia officers was considered urgent. The leadership of the NKVD RSFSR emphasized that the selection of militia officers was possible only with the support of national party and professional organizations. To this end, on July 4, 1929 the directive on the staffing of the workers' and peasants' militia and the regulation of its social composition came into force. In November 1929, the Statute on the Militia Administration of the NKVD RSFSR was adopted [12].

The NKVD RSFSR system did not have a single training center, which did not correspond to the general development trends of the Soviet state and led to certain difficulties in the work. The Accounting and Distribution Department of the NKVD RSFSR was engaged in

personnel accounting and distribution, had a small staff and did not pay due attention to the training of personnel. Therefore, on July 11, 1930, the "Accounting and Distribution Department" of the NKVD RSFSR was transformed into the "Personnel Department" and this department was established as a single body for the selection, education, training, accounting and distribution of militia personnel and personnel [13].

The organization of personnel management required the centralization of the personal records of responsible employees of the NKVD and its local agencies. Consequently, on August 2, 1930, NKVD instruction № 402 "On the study, accounting and distribution of nomenclature positions, staff and accounting of all employees of the Narkomat, administrative and communal bodies" came into force. [14].

In the pre-war years, the personnel apparatus of the NKVD bodies in the center and in the field was improved, their role and responsibility in the work with the personnel was strengthened. By order of the NKVD of the USSR, the Regulation "On the Personnel Department of the NKVD of the USSR" was issued. According to the Statute, the Personnel Department is the central apparatus of the NKVD of the USSR and is created to perform its duties in the matters of selection, training, placement, transfer and dismissal of NKVD personnel. The Personnel Department of the NKVD of the USSR managed the personnel departments of the main departments (divisions) of the People's Commissariat of Internal Affairs [15].

On July 3, 1936, the Central Executive Committee of the former USSR adopted the Regulation of the NKVD of the USSR "On Service in the Workers' and Peasants' Militia". [16]. This regulation determined the procedure of recruiting candidates to the militia, appointments to positions, and the rights and duties of militia chiefs. At that time, special attention was paid to the professional training of militia officers in order to improve their literacy and to develop them into versatile professionals [17].

Until 1931 the "workers' militia" operated within the system of local authorities, then it was centralized in the system of local People's Commissariat, and in 1946 - in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the former Soviet state [18].

World War II had a negative impact on the human resources policy of internal affairs bodies. On the first day of the battle, 25 percent of the most experienced and qualified personnel left for the front, and most of them did not return after the battle. The number of personnel trained for internal affairs bodies in educational institutions was also halved [18].

After World War II, the internal affairs bodies faced problems related to human resources policy. First of all, the internal affairs bodies were filled with people who had courageously fought the Nazis during World War II. And the remaining vacancies are filled by those unfit for service: the disabled, pensioners, women, and others. 3.9% of the total number of employees have completed or incomplete higher education, 64.4% have primary education. Due to the lack of quality and qualified personnel, criminal cases were initiated against 42,849 employees by a special inspection of the NKVD. They were investigated and prosecuted accordingly [19].

In March 1946, in accordance with the law "On the Transformation of the Council of People's Commissars into the USSR Council of Ministers", the name of the USSR IHN (NKVD) was changed to the USSR Ministry of Internal Affairs (MIA). [20].

In February 1947, personnel departments were established in the Main Directorate of Militia of the USSR Ministry of Internal Affairs, as well as in local, republican and regional

militia departments. On July 22, 1947, a special inspection for the investigation of violations committed by MIA employees during the performance of official duties, as well as in off-duty time, was created in the Personnel Directorate of the USSR MIA.

As for the system of normative legal acts regulating social relations related to the personnel of internal affairs bodies, the Decree of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the former USSR of February 15, 1962 "On increasing liability for infringement of life, health and dignity of militia officers and people's vigilantes". In addition, the Decree of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the former USSR of October 23, 1973 "On special ranks of heads and chiefs of internal affairs bodies", the Decree of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the former USSR of July 8, 1973 "On the basic rights and duties of the Soviet militia in the fight against crime and the protection of public order", the Decree of the Interior Ministry of the former USSR, which entered into force on August 1, 1975 regulated the allowance of the personnel of internal affairs bodies, etc. [21].

On August 17, 1962 the Regulation "On Soviet Militia" was adopted, which, taking into account the changed historical conditions, further clarified the main tasks of the militia, its place and role in the system of state authorities. New approaches to the selection, education and training of militia officers were needed. Therefore, a department for political and educational work, along with a special inspectorate for personnel, was created as part of the Interior Ministry's personnel department. The Department of Political and Educational Work, which was part of the Personnel Administration, was effective in educating Soviet militiamen, as it changed the consciousness and behavior of many people who served in the militia and was able to educate a true citizen, dedicated to his cause and the Soviet state, and conscientiously fulfilled his duty [22].

The personnel service in the internal affairs system was able to fully meet the needs of the Soviet state and fully perform the tasks assigned to them. This structure of personnel service remained unchanged until 1991.

The Decree of the Council of Ministers of the former Soviet Union of October 23, 1973 "On Approval of the Regulations for the service of regular and managerial staff of the internal affairs bodies" approved the requirements for candidates in the selection of staff for service in the internal affairs bodies. In accordance with paragraphs 3-6 of these Regulations it is defined that healthy citizens not younger than 18 years, morally mature, committed to the socialist homeland and communist construction, have the necessary training and are fit for military service. are accepted for service in the internal affairs bodies of the USSR. [23].

Based on the above, the process of formation of the Soviet militia cadre in 1917-1991 can be divided into three periods:

1) the period from October 1917 (the formation of the Soviet state and the Soviet militia) to 1923 (the beginning of the administrative reform): the initial legal basis for working with the personnel was developed;

2) the period from 1924 (accounting and distribution department of the NKVD RSFSR) to the end of the 1930s (adoption of the Regulation on the NKVD RSFSR Personnel Department of May 3, 1939): the adoption of regulations related to the selection and placement of personnel;

3) The period from 1940 to 1991: improvement of normative-legal acts related to the selection and placement of personnel.

Thus, in the initial period of development of the Soviet militia was created a legal framework for working with personnel.

It can be recognized that the genesis of the personnel apparatus of the Soviet militia was distinguished by a number of features. Firstly, the emergence of cadre apparatus was associated with tendencies for centralization of Soviet militia at the state level, which was to become a pillar of the totalitarian state. Secondly, normative legal acts of that period legislated the structure of personnel bodies, the scope and content of personnel functions, the powers of officials responsible for organizing work with employees. Thirdly, the selection and placement of personnel was carried out on a scientific basis, elements of forecasting and planning future needs in qualified personnel of different levels were applied [24].

Initial transformations aimed at improving the material and technical condition of internal affairs bodies and the introduction of a system of training of qualified national personnel were carried out during the period of independence and the transition period of our country. In particular, on October 25, 1991 on the basis of the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan № 270 the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Uzbek SSR was transformed into the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This decree approved the position and structure of the Ministry. Later this date was designated as the day of internal affairs officers in our country [25].

In general, the system of internal affairs bodies of our country has passed by now a long and difficult way. This path has played an important role in its transformation into a real human-oriented structure.

References:

1. Spipyna E.A. Legal ensuring for the formation of human resources of internal affairs bodies. Abstract dis. cand. legal Sciences M, 2003. – P. 14.
2. Chuprov V.M. Administrative-legal and organizational means of ensuring human resources policy in the internal affairs bodies. Abstract dis. cand. legal Sciences M., 2005. - S. 14., SU RSFSR.-1917 -Jfe I. – P. 15.
3. Gorobtsov V.I., Gonyukhov S.O. Russian militia in uniform: textbook. M., 2000. P. 65–66.
4. On the organization of the Soviet Workers' and Peasants' Militia (instruction): resolution of the NKVD of the RSFSR of October 13, 1918 // News of the Central Executive Committee of the USSR and the All-Russian Central Executive Committee. 1918. № 223SU of the RSFSR.– 1918. – № 75 – P. 813
5. Razuvaeva N.I. Selection and certification of personnel of internal affairs bodies (administrative-legal and organizational aspects). dis. cand. legal Sciences Voronezh, 2014. – 215 pages, A.N. Savluk. Mechanisms for the implementation of state human resources policy in the context of modern administrative reform specialty: Abstract of the thesis. dis. cand. polit. Sciences. St. Petersburg, 2013. – P. 14.
6. URL: <https://qriiv.uz/uz/menu/iiv-tarihi> (Date of application: 18.02.2023).
7. URL: <https://iiv.uz/oz/pages/vazirlik-tarixi> (Date of application: 15.02.2023).
8. Spipyna E.A. Legal ensuring for the formation of human resources of internal affairs bodies. Abstract dis. cand. legal Sciences. M., 2003. – P. 14., I. A. Andreeva, E. S. Zaitseva The history of the internal affairs bodies of Russia // Textbook. 2017. Omsk. S. 276.

9. Kamalova G. T. Organizational and legal foundations of the activities of the Soviet police (1920-1923) // Bulletin of the South Ural State University 2007. № 4. P. 17-18., Cherdakov O. I. People's Commissariat of Internal Affairs in the law enforcement system of the Soviet states (1917-1936) // Law and Politics. 2002. № 3. P. 120.
10. Kokurin A., Petrov N. NKVD: structure, functions, personnel // Free Thought. 1997. № 6. P. 103., Actual problems of the history of the Soviet police. Collection of scientific papers. Minsk, 1991., Mulukaev R.C., Kartashov H.H. Police of Russia (1917-1993). Historical and legal essay. Orel, 1995., Epifanov A.E., Kantemirov A.V. Department of Internal Affairs of Russia: History of Formation and Development: Textbook. Volgograd, 2005; Didenko A.A., Menyailo D.V. History of internal affairs bodies: Textbook. Belgorod, 2005.
11. Chuprov V.M. Administrative-legal and organizational means of ensuring human resources policy in the internal affairs bodies. Abstract dis. cand. legal Sciences M., 2005. - P. 14., Didenko A.A., Menyailo D.V. History of internal affairs bodies: Textbook. Belgorod, 2005.
12. Spipyina E.A. Legal ensuring for the formation of human resources of internal affairs bodies. Abstract dis. cand. legal Sciences. M., 2003. - P. 14.
13. Razuvaeva N.I. Selection and certification of personnel of internal affairs bodies (administrative-legal and organizational aspects). dis. cand. legal Sciences Voronezh, 2014. - 215 pages.
14. Reznikov A.A. The structure and human resources policy of the internal affairs bodies of the USSR in 1945-1953. Abstract dis. cand. history Sciences. M., 2012. P. 35.
15. Reznikov A.A. The structure and human resources policy of the internal affairs bodies of the USSR in 1945-1953. Abstract dis. cand. history Sciences. M., 2012. -P. 35.
16. Mulukaev R. S., Malygin A. Ya., Epifanov A. E. History of domestic internal affairs bodies: a textbook for universities. M., 2005. P. 195.
17. SU RSFSR.-1917 – Jfe I. – P. 15 ‘, SU RSFSR.-1918. – № 75 – P. 813, SZ USSR. – 193 p. – № 36. – P. 316.
18. Reznikov A.A. Human resources policy of the internal affairs bodies of the USSR in the post-war years (1945-1946). // Bulletin of Moscow University. Series 21. Management (State and Society). June 2011. № 2. pp. 124-132.
19. Reznikov A.A. The structure and human resources policy of the internal affairs bodies of the USSR in 1945-1953. Abstract dis. cand. history Sciences M, 2012. – P. 17.
20. Collection of laws of the USSR and decrees of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR 1945-1946. M., 1947. P. 13.
21. Chuprov V.M. Administrative-legal and organizational means of ensuring human resources policy in the internal affairs bodies. Abstract dis. cand. legal Sciences M, 2005.
22. Kokurin A., Petrov N. NKVD: structure, functions, personnel // Free Thought. 1997. № 6. P. 103., Actual problems of the history of the Soviet police. Collection of scientific papers. Minsk, 1991.
23. Gazette of the USSR Armed Forces. – 1962. – № 8. – Art. 3., Gazette of the USSR Armed Forces – 1973. – № 43 – Art. 603, Gazette of the USSR Armed Forces. – 1973. – № 24. – Art. 309.
24. Kokurin A., Petrov N. NKVD: structure, functions, personnel // Free Thought. 1997. № 6. S. 103.
25. URL: <https://iiv.uz/oz/pages/vazirlik-tarixi> (Date of application: 21.02.2023).